

ISic0269

I.Sicily inscription 0269

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(ecimus) · Annius Rufus

2. vix(it) · ann(is) · XL

3. Numitoria · Hagne

4. con(iugi) · car(issimo)

Apparatus

Text based upon Bitto 2001

Gruterus: Aninius

Translation (en)

To Decimus Annius Rufus, by Numitoria Hagne, his wife.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284763

EDR 033603

EDCS 21900299

PHI 313697

Bibliography

Gualtherus, G. 1624. Siciliæ obiacentium insular. et Bruttiorum antiquæ tabulæ, cum animadversionib. Messanae. At no.19

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.6980 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At xv

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